

Survey on best practices in traffic state predictions

Ynte Vanderhoydonc¹, Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl¹, Panagiotis Fafoutellis², Eleni I. Vlahogianni², Eleni Mantouka², Arka Ghosh³, Juan S. Angarita-Zapata^{3,4,*}, Athina Tympakianaki⁴, Antonio D. Masegosa^{3,5}, and Siegfried Mercelis¹

¹University of Antwerp - imec, IDLab - Faculty of Applied Engineering, Sint-Pietersvliet 7, 2000 Antwerp, Belgium

²National Technical University of Athens, Department of Transportation Planning and Engineering, School of Civil Engineering, 5, Iroon Polytechniou Str., Athens 15773, Greece

³Deusto Institute of Technology (DeustoTech), Faculty of Engineering, University of Deusto, 48007 Bilbao, Spain

⁴Aimsun, Barcelona, Spain

⁵Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, 48009 Bilbao, Spain

* Corresponding affiliation is Aimsun, work started while author was at Deusto Institute of Technology

Corresponding author: Ynte Vanderhoydonc (e-mail: ynte.vanderhoydonc@uantwerpen.be).

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ABSTRACT Efficient dynamic transport management necessitates adequate robust models and techniques for effective traffic monitoring and forecasting. Accurate traffic supply forecasting is crucial in anticipating and mitigating traffic congestion. However, the field of network traffic state prediction is characterized by diverse methodologies and tools, encompassing both data-driven and simulation-based approaches, and selecting which of them to use and how to define the appropriate problem formulation and relevant parameters is not always a trivial task. This paper provides a comprehensive overview of best practices employed in state-of-the-art traffic state prediction models, emphasizing guidelines for developing accurate and robust prediction frameworks. We present guidelines that address varying requirements for different traffic forecasting applications, considering parameters such as model scope and usage, data requirements, strategy specifics, output evaluation, generalization, and implementation. These guidelines facilitate the comparison of contemporary traffic supply forecasting models, with a particular focus on deep learning models, which have demonstrated superior performance over traditional statistical or machine learning methods. This comparison, based on the guidelines, includes various state-of-the-art traffic supply predictions models that utilize deep learning techniques.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic traffic management systems aim to be efficient in terms of congestion reduction and prevention, mitigation of environmental impact through CO₂ reduction, increased safety, and economic advantages [1]. Furthermore, multimodal networks require an even more coordinated traffic management plan, as different transport operators and authorities are involved, for synchronising and optimizing the operations in multimodal transport networks in a dynamic and adaptive way [2]. Although many cities have deployed dynamic traffic management systems, their ability to estimate transport network states and provide short-term predictions of congestion evolution, which would enable timely interventions and decision making, is limited. Adequate models and techniques need to be developed to support the monitoring and forecasting of the traffic conditions, including both the transport demand and supply, under various recurrent and non-recurrent conditions (e.g., incidents, sport events, work zones, etc.) and in the context

of multimodality. A key component for the development of efficient traffic management systems is the availability of heterogeneous data in terms of both transport demand and supply, which can be harmonized and fused to feed the system with adequate information to enable the decision-making process for traffic operations.

With the term demand, we refer to the number of trips from and to certain areas/zones, which can be described as an Origin-Destination (O-D) matrix. On the other hand, traffic supply refers to the traffic conditions at specific locations (e.g., road sections) or for the whole network, with mean speed and traffic volume being used as indicators in this work (other indicators can be used as well, e.g., occupancy, travel times, etc.).

This work was supported by the TANGENT project. In summary, TANGENT is developing new complementary Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools for optimizing traffic operations in a coordinated and dynamic manner from a multimodal perspective and considering

automated/non-automated vehicles, passengers, and freight transport. TANGENT will improve knowledge and management of mobility flows along a range of transport modes. In addition, it will enable the implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions, services, and business models. The project will contribute to more efficient traffic management, facilitating multimodal networks, accelerating the transition towards connected and automated mobility, reducing pollutant emissions and congestion, improving safety and security, and reducing the cost of mobility for all. This paper results from the exploration and analysis of traffic prediction techniques performed in one of the work packages of the TANGENT project, namely transport prediction & simulation models.

Traffic state forecasting research has more than 40 years of history, yet the specific field is fragmented in terms of methodologies and tools implemented [3]. Traditional approaches for traffic prediction, including statistical and time series approaches (e.g., ARIMA, decomposition, Vector Autoregressive models, etc.) present limitations when capturing the spatial and temporal relationships of complex, non-linear traffic patterns [4]. The aforementioned issues has turned researchers' attention to more novel data-driven approaches, such as Machine Learning and Deep Learning. It has been noticed that, in recent literature, complex Deep Learning structures are treated as "black boxes", meaning that they are blindly implemented, due to their ability to capture these complex spatiotemporal relations. However, in order to achieve their full potential and depending on the scope of the application, different approaches should be considered, as well as specific parameters of the problem statement should be taken into account. In this paper, we provide some suggestions regarding good practices that should be followed when developing traffic forecasting models and provide a thorough review of state-of-the-art methods. In addition, we proceed to developing and evaluating the most prominent of them.

A. DATA-DRIVEN APPROACHES

Traffic estimation and prediction have been tackled from different modeling perspectives during the last years. The approaches commonly reported in transportation literature include data-driven methods, simulation-based approaches, and hybrid methods.

With the increase in data collection and computational resources, data-driven approaches have been introduced in transportation literature to capture the features present in traffic data and use them to predict the traffic state. The two main approaches are statistical and Machine Learning (ML) methods. The autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) family of models is an example of statistical approaches for traffic forecasting [5]. Other statistical approaches used for traffic forecasting include nonparametric regression method [6], Bayesian model [7], hidden Markov model [8] and Kalman filter model [9]. Support Vector Machines, k-Nearest Neighbors or Random Forest [10], [3] are examples of traditional ML methods, that

are applied to traffic forecasting. These traditional methods are suitable approaches when dealing with traffic scenarios where predictions are desired to be made at a single point on the road or in one/more corridors. However, as point-to-point data sources have progressively been incorporated into traffic estimation and prediction (e.g., GPS data), traditional ML methods face limitations when capturing the spatial and temporal relationships of traffic patterns [11], [4], [12]. For this type of network-wide (area-wide) prediction problem, the common approach in terms of data-driven approaches is to use Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), which allows exploiting the temporal and spatial characteristics of traffic data. With the ever-growing data collection, deep learning techniques started to improve and surpassed the traditional methods in performance [13]. These approaches scale with the amount of available data because of their high representational power. Meaning, as the quantity and variety of traffic data increases, deep learning techniques become even more advantageous. They can effectively learn and adapt from this abundance of information, providing more accurate and comprehensive traffic predictions than traditional methods. Furthermore, learning efficiency is an advantage of deep learning techniques as well. Traffic hidden dependencies are extracted via feature engineering in training traditional ML methods, which might suffer from subjectivity. On the other hand, DNNs propose the learning strategy end to end, where these patterns are automatically learnt via different neural networks.

B. SIMULATION-BASED APPROACHES

Traffic simulation models are used to study various complex and large-scale problems, from transport planning to evaluation of traffic management strategies as well as for the estimation and prediction of the transport network traffic state [14], [15], [16]. Unlike the data-driven methods, simulation models do not rely on historical or real-time traffic data but rather simulate traffic, as no historical data is available when developing a road network. A traffic simulation model can estimate future traffic levels to evaluate the suitability of a transportation system design; however, a model cannot predict the next state of traffic based on historical and real-time data [17].

Models for traffic simulation were first developed by [18]. The movement of vehicles is simulated in these models through an Origin-Destination matrix (OD), which describes a region's movement. Each cell in the OD matrix represents the number of trips from the origin to the destination. The row expresses the origin, and the column expresses the destination. Traffic simulation models can be classified as microscopic, macroscopic, or mesoscopic [17].

In the microscopic perspective, each driver and their interactions are modeled using a multi-agent system where every agent records information or behavior for each trip [19]. Cellular automata (CA) is a typical microscopic simulation method in which a road is divided into cells that a vehicle can occupy, and time is discretized into steps. The CA model reproduces a wide variety of traffic phenomena

well and is numerically very efficient due to its simplicity. A combination of this model with OD predictions has been used to develop network-wide traffic predictions [17], [20].

The macroscopic analysis evaluates each road segment's density, speed, and vehicle count [21]. Static and dynamic traffic assignment are two methods that allocate traffic on a simulated road network. Temporal OD matrices are necessary for models of traffic flows over time in dynamic assignment models, but static assignment models only require a static OD matrix of overall trip demand of actors [22]. In comparison to older statistical and machine learning models, modern neural networks have superior performance. However, their data-hungry nature makes it challenging to train them in cities and scenarios with little available data. This has led [23] to develop a simulator that provides an excessive dataset for training neural networks and statistical methods. In addition to macroscopic models, formulas derived primarily from hydrodynamics can be used to simulate changes in traffic density and vehicle count over time in urban areas [24], [17]. Mesoscopic approaches have the advantage of modeling a wide range of phenomena, such as traffic signals, freeway merging, weaving sections, or high-occupancy traveling lanes [25], [17].

C. HYBRID APPROACHES

For the category of hybrid methods, two or more algorithms are combined to find synergies that improve their isolated performance. One advantage of hybrid methods is the use of simulation-based approaches for unseen traffic patterns. The main limitation of the data-driven approach is when it hasn't seen the traffic pattern before, e.g., when an incident occurs. This can be tackled by integrating data-driven and simulation models [26].

D. OUTLINE PAPER

The structure of this paper is outlined as follows. Section II introduces the guidelines proposed by the authors for developing robust traffic prediction models. These guidelines serve as a basis for evaluating current state-of-the-art models in traffic supply forecasting, covered in section III. Section III begins with an introduction to traffic supply forecasting, highlights differences from previous surveys and reviews, and details state-of-the-art models. It concludes with a comparative analysis of these models according to the guidelines from section II. Section IV discusses key research directions in this field, and section V presents the conclusion.

II. GUIDELINES FOR DEVELOPING ROBUST PREDICTION MODELS

This paper introduces best practices to support researchers and practitioners in developing prediction models for traffic forecasting (TF). With this aim in mind, this section starts by describing guidelines for developing accurate and robust prediction models. The various approaches to tackle TF were described in the introduction, namely data-driven, simulation-based and hybrid approaches. The focus of this section is on

guidelines to develop such prediction models, by defining the scope, data needs, modeling strategy, etc. These guidelines are used in the following section to compare state-of-the-art

models in the context of deep learning TF.

The sophisticated modeling techniques and algorithms that will be discussed later give researchers and practitioners a bounty of options to develop high-performance prediction models. Traffic conditions forecasting, however, is usually treated as a spatio-temporal time series prediction problem, with various implications in traffic management, planning and policymaking. Therefore, it should not be treated as any other deep learning prediction task, where only accuracy matters, but the most suitable modeling technique, depending on various parameters, should be chosen very carefully. In addition, interpretability, real-time operation and update and simplicity are some of the properties the model should retain to be exploited in real-world conditions.

It becomes clear that TF is a challenging task that incorporates numerous parameters that must be determined, such as the modeling strategy, data collection and pre-processing, the generalization of the results and the implementation in real-world conditions. These challenging aspects must be carefully considered when developing prediction models. This section addresses this by considering the interconnected parameters visualized below, which should be considered during model development.

A. RELATION OF THE SCOPE AND USAGE WITH THE MODELING TECHNIQUE

There are different requirements, for different forecasting applications, in terms of modeling techniques, data needs, etc. As discussed in more detail in the next sections, the supply is related to the ability of the road network to serve the demand and is measured by the traffic flow, speed or travel time of the network's road sections, while the demand patterns are commonly expressed as dynamic (time-dependent) origin-destination flow matrices and each cell in the matrix represents the number of trips from an origin to a destination for a specific mode of transport.

So, the first decision that should be made by the practitioner is based on the scope of the model. For example, distinguish between supply and demand side prediction.

There are very different approaches for the prediction of supply and demand, as well as different data requirements, for example, for the onset of congestion prediction or origin-destination information predictions respectively. Researchers and practitioners should understand the differences and follow the most appropriate approach depending on the scope each time and not proceed to apply unsuitable models without critically thinking. The most popular modeling techniques will be presented in detail in the remainder of this paper.

Furthermore, they should determine the application in which the model is going to be exploited and its exact requirements. Different types of use, such as real-time predictive management in different levels, i.e., operational, tactical, and strategic policymaking, may involve also very different approaches in terms of modeling and data acquisition. The scope and usage of the model will also influence the selection of the parameters to be predicted, the spatio-temporal extent of the predictions, as well as the modeling tools to be used. The scope and usage are categorized into 1) local and network level predictions and 2) prediction horizon. A description of each category is included below.

1) SCOPE: LOCAL AND NETWORK LEVEL PREDICTIONS

TF refers to either local predictions or network-wide predictions. Local prediction is the prediction of the future conditions at a single point/road section where a loop detector is usually installed, using as input historical data from the same detector or/and several correlated detectors. On the other hand, network-wide predictions correspond to predictions on points or road sections of an entire road network. They integrate multiple input (e.g., historical data from multiple loop detectors) and output variables (e.g., output from predictions on neighbouring road sections).

Regarding the scope, the network-wide prediction of the traffic conditions is usually performed in an urban environment, where there is a higher deviation of the traffic parameters, a higher possibility of extreme conditions and complex demand (origin-destination trips) and supply relations, compared to arterials and freeways. In an urban context, where policies should be applied and decision regarding traffic management should be taken, network-wide approaches are significantly more suitable, as they provide information for the entire road-network and insights into the corresponding relations between different locations. In addition, although it is a more complex problem to solve, it has more scientific interest as well.

The separation between the two types of predictions will also determine the amount of data that is required, as is discussed below in section B. For network-level predictions data covering the whole network or study area of interest are needed. As discussed in section C, DL structures and simulation are more suitable for network-wide predictions since the wider the spatial coverage of the model, the more complex the spatial and temporal relations that emerge.

Because of the increased complexity and the more sophisticated modeling approach, as well as the higher data requirement, efficient and accurate network-wide prediction is still an open issue in the TF literature. The practitioner should find a balance between the model's complexity and performance, especially when using complex DL architectures.

2) APPLICATION: PREDICTION HORIZON

Another critical consideration for developing a traffic prediction model is the desirable prediction horizon. We divide horizons depending on what kind of variables are relevant for the prediction:

- Predictions < 15min (especially those with horizon < 5min): in these cases, the last observed values have a very high correlation with the value to predict. So, it is easy to reach high accuracy only relying on the last minutes of data, and - if available - data from the neighbouring sections. In these cases, simple and fast models are usually the best choice (they reach high accuracy easily) and if info of neighbouring sections is available, then flow propagation models can be also used.
- Prediction horizons between 15 and 60min: in these cases, last observed values are important, but as the horizon increases, the type of day becomes more important (in terms of correlation). For example, with a horizon of 1h it the historical average of the time of day and day of week becomes more important than the last observed values. Therefore, for this kind of predictions, models must deal with both short term and long-term temporal relationships.
- Predictions > 60min: the last observed values are less and less relevant as the horizon increases, so models must rely on long-term relationships (e.g., on the type of day).
- Predictions > several weeks: this kind of predictions must rely on the type of day (long-term relationships) as with horizons > 60min, however, due to the distance between the prediction and the moment that is predicted, models are more sensible to data drift.

In real-world conditions, the choice of the predicting horizon mostly depends on the application that the model will be used for. Short-term prediction models are suitable for real-time decision-making and traffic management, travel time estimation and route planning, while long-term predictions can be exploited for policymaking and planning. The practitioner, therefore, should consider the overall aim of the model and the area of application.

In each of the two cases, data of the corresponding resolution are needed, i.e., high-resolution data for short-term forecasting, while data of lower resolution can be used for long-term forecasting. Consequently, the predicting horizon affects the data requirements, which are discussed in the next section.

B. DEFINE DATA NEEDS

Data are nowadays an asset for the scientific community, especially for researchers that are involved in model development. The rapid evolution of computing and telecommunication systems, as well as connected smart devices and the Internet of Things, have led to the Big Data era, where vast amounts of data are being collected and made available. The latter facts have influenced a lot the shift from statistical modeling to data-driven approaches during the last couple of decades.

Traffic data can be provided by loop detectors that are installed in numerous road networks or by the GPS signals of vehicles or smart devices of drivers. Although the number of available datasets is always increasing, still no such data are available for a significant number of cities. Therefore, the first limitation to consider is related to the availability of the required data, and, more specifically, the type of data that are needed, their granularity and their quantity.

A network-level prediction model would require data covering the whole network or study area of interest. Furthermore, when e.g., predictions $< 15\text{min}$ are requested, data of high temporal resolution are needed, while for predictions $> 60\text{min}$ lower resolution data can also be exploited. As far as it concerns the scope of the prediction, for supply prediction, multimodal and heterogeneous data sources can be used to enhance the predictions. This kind of data also require special handling and data fusion techniques to be exploited for the same model.

Lastly, it is widely understood that complex DL structures require huge amounts of data to train and to achieve stable and decent performance. Furthermore, data diversity (e.g., in terms of time and seasonal coverage) matters. As such, not only the modeling technique defines the data needs, but also data availability determines if certain modeling techniques can be implemented. So, the practitioners should first define the type and quantity of the required data for each specific task (based on the above general rules) and then, depending on their availability, choose a suitable modeling approach. Furthermore, guidelines to cope with missing or incomplete data are important when working with real-world data:

- The first step in training a DL model is checking whether the data has the required quality, e.g., via visual inspection of data for extreme missing values and fluctuations and statistical methods of anomaly detection [27].
- Resampling is a crucial part as well. It is the process of changing the frequency of the data by either aggregating (down sampling) or performing up sampling. Up sampling can help the model to better learn the transition between two distant observations.
- Missing values are ubiquitous in time series data. For example, the missing values can be caused by the malfunction of the recording device or its communication service to the storage facility. Furthermore, it can be caused by the lack of data.
- Deep learning models can handle a fair number of missing values. There are several ways to mitigate these missing values. Filling values can be done using

straightforward algorithms like Forward Fill (replacing with the most recent observation) and Backward Fill (replacing with the first following available observation), or some other algorithms that are a bit more complex, like Imputation (mean, median, mode), interpolation (linear, polynomial, and spline), or using simpler Machine Learning algorithms to predict missing values resorting to observed values.

- Normalizing the dataset is crucial before feeding the data into the model. It means transforming the inputs to a similar scale, usually between 0 and 1. This stabilizes deep learning models and improves accuracy.

C. MODELING STRATEGY

The modeling strategy has already been mentioned a lot in the previous paragraphs and sections, as it influences (and is influenced by) all other aspects. There are three main categories of modeling techniques that are applied in traffic forecasting: statistical modeling, machine learning and deep learning, and simulation-based models. The main differences between the data-driven approaches can be summarized as follows: deep learning and, secondarily, ML models require larger amounts of data and have been observed to have more accurate performance when their data needs are satisfied but lack the interpretability of statistical models and demand more computational resources and time to train.

Therefore, unless a sufficiently big dataset is available, the practitioner should better avoid developing a DL model, especially a very complex one. Also, in real-world applications, if the corresponding city authority, for example, that is going to use the model (e.g., road network operator) lacks the computational resources needed to train and maintain the model and the relevant datasets, complex DL models should be avoided as well. In addition, the interpretability of the results is a very useful property of the Simulation-based prediction model in many real-world situations, which DL models usually lack. For example, it is vital to detect the most influential factors of increased congestion and not only predict its occurrence, to take measures to alleviate it. In such cases, deep learning should be avoided.

On the other hand, deep learning and simulation are superior compared to statistical models when making a network-wide prediction using high dimensional input and output space. Also, as traffic data are, most of the times, non-stationary and their interrelations are very complex and non-linear, deep learning and machine learning models have an advantage compared to statistical models. Indeed, different DL models can extract the spatial and temporal relations of the road network and imitate its complex and non-linear mechanisms, while not being subject to any constraints. Finally, their input data can be represented in more complicated structures such as images or graphs, which are more meaningful and accurate, especially for a road network. On the other hand, simpler models can be used efficiently for local predictions.

Besides the network-wide predictions, simulation is needed in the case of non-recurrent events (e.g., accidents) for which historical data are not available. In such cases, once the incident is detected, simulation-based approaches are used to replicate and predict its impacts (e.g., congestion, demand changes, rerouting) which is not feasible through data-driven approaches.

Furthermore, hybrid methods can combine the strengths of both data-driven and simulation-based approaches. The role of data-driven predictions in feeding the simulation is two-fold:

- The local predictions can be transformed into traffic states (such as aggregate traffic flow measures) and be given as input to the simulation models.
- Data-driven predictions can feed the demand prediction models, which can use real-time predicted traffic measurements for the locations that data are available to update the demand for the next intervals.

Despite the above, a sophisticated feature selection strategy is always encouraged, to reduce the dimensionality of the input space and the overall complexity of the modeling approach, by exploiting the most relevant and correlated input variables. In contrast, a “black-box” approach including all the available inputs, may prevent the convergence of the model and unnecessarily increase training time and computational complexity. Another way to reduce the complexity of the model is to discretize the output of the model, which usually takes continuous values (e.g., speed, traffic flow), into a few categories. The categories may correspond to free flow, moderate, congested, etc. traffic conditions. The latter depends on the type of output variable values required to fulfill the model’s aim.

As far as it concerns traffic forecasting, it can be performed either at a macroscopic or microscopic level, based on the expected outcome. Macroscopic level predictions are suitable for predicting traffic flow levels, delays, or average speed of road sections at a network level, while microscopic level predictions go deeper in a more personalized, agent level, allowing, for example, the estimation of travel times of individual users.

Based on recent evidence, there is not a universal best approach for any given situation and the practitioner should consider all the above parameters before deciding on a modeling strategy to follow.

D. MODEL OUTPUT EVALUATION

Along with the model development, the practitioner should decide on an evaluation strategy for its results. As observed in recent literature, there are various criteria to evaluate a model. First, an error metric is used to compare the actual and the predicted values. Among the different existing metrics, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is the most popular, because it gives a straightforward estimate of the accuracy of the model, as it has the same units of measurement as the actual value. Moreover, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), which are also very frequently used, set a higher

penalty for instances with extremely high error values, as they are proportional to the square of the error’s value. Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) is used to compare with other models, fitted on different datasets. If the problem is modelled as a classification one, e.g., predict the level of traffic congestion as a categorical variable, relevant metrics should be used, namely accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score.

Except for the accuracy of the prediction, the practitioner should also assess the following properties of the model: complexity, how time-consuming its training process is, and at which level the results are interpretable and transferable. These properties are very often mentioned in recent literature and are sometimes as important as the absolute value of the error. Therefore, the practitioner should consider the above factors and evaluate each developed model based on them as well. Besides, the accuracy metrics are not directly comparable between models of very different complexities and datasets with different sizes and characteristics. Thus, there is a need for a more holistic evaluation approach and the definition of benchmarking datasets and models.

When developing a model, it is essential to optimize both its parameters and hyperparameters to get the optimal performance. Parameters refer to the internal variables of the model that are learned during the training process, usually using gradient descent in deep learning. The hyperparameter refers to external settings that control the learning procedure, e.g., the learning rate.

Hyperparameter tuning is a crucial step that runs alongside the model’s training phase. However, this process can be challenging, time-consuming, and computationally expensive for deep learning models due to having a big search space and the need to train the model for each hyperparameter candidate. Together with the search space, computational resources and the problem complexity are the main influential factors within the training process. Similarly, in traffic simulation, before running an instance of a simulation-based prediction model, all the demand and supply parameters that are integrated into the transport model should be carefully calibrated so that the latter is representative of the real road network.

A model whose parameters’ values are not optimized would produce systematic errors and would not perform according to each full potential. Thus, the practitioners should not disregard this step.

E. GENERALIZATION

Generalization has arisen as a major issue of modeling traffic conditions and remains a quite under-researched area. The effort, time, and resources (data, etc.) needed to develop a new prediction model, especially DL models make it worth for practitioners and researchers to consider and evaluate the possibility of using (or “transferring”) an already developed model for predicting the traffic conditions at another point or road network. In deep learning, the concept of transferability is usually exploited to cope with the lack of relevant data,

e.g., at a road network or section, by using an already trained model of a similar road network or section, respectively. Some references regarding transfer learning for TF are [28], [29].

After a short fine-tuning process, it is possible that such a model can be transferred, maintaining a decent accuracy. Given the significant importance and the utility of generalization, the practitioner should examine if it's possible.

F. IMPLEMENTATION (MOVE TO PRODUCTION)

Lately, there are a few researchers and practitioners that, without underestimating the effectiveness and the potential of DL models, are concerned about its overwhelming use in TF. They argue that such complex structures are not efficient for real-world exploitation and that practitioners should focus on less computationally expensive and more interpretable models.

More specifically, when they must be applied in real-world conditions, the models should maintain some additional specific properties. Firstly, a very complex model that demands high computational resources is not usually suitable for real-world problems. Thus, the practitioner should at least ensure that the resources, as well as the required amount of data, are available. This applies to both DL and simulation-based models. This kind of models' fitting and operation are also time-consuming, which limits the chances of their deployment in real-time applications.

Moreover, a model that is interpretable and reveals the spatio-temporal relations between road sections can be used for policy- and decision-making, e.g., in case a section closes because of an accident, the administrator would be able to identify the road sections that are going to be immediately impacted and take measures. Most DL models are non-interpretable and, although they provide very accurate predictions in normal traffic conditions, their performance drops significantly during extreme conditions and unexpected events.

Furthermore, there is a need for retraining TF models over time, taking the evolution of data and/or network into account, to ensure its accuracy.

Lastly, the practitioner should ensure a stable data flow within the appropriate period (depending on the specific application) and the validity and accuracy of the data collection process to use the corresponding model in real-world conditions.

III. DEEP LEARNING MODELS FOR TRAFFIC SUPPLY FORECASTING AND COMPARISON BASED ON GUIDELINES

This section builds on the guidelines in the previous section to apply state-of-the-art deep learning models for traffic forecasting, as discussed in section C. Before we proceed with the guideline-based comparison, section A provides a literature review focused on survey and review papers of

deep learning methods, while section B presents an overview of the latest state-of-the-art models.

A. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on TF reports the application of diverse Deep Learning (DL) methods, such as convolutional-recurrent and graph neural networks, among others (e.g., [30]). This variety of DL techniques has led to several survey and review papers between 2019 and 2023 [13], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [36]. As a common denominator, these papers mainly focus on reviewing, characterizing, and testing state-of-the-art DL methods in different TF scenarios, as described below.

In [13] the authors proposed a taxonomy to categorize TF problems from both traffic and a supervised learning perspective. The taxonomy aimed at unifying and consolidating categorization criteria related to traffic and it introduced new criteria to classify the problems in terms of how they are modelled from a supervised regression approach. Then, TF literature, from 2000 to 2019, was categorized using this taxonomy. From this literature classification, it was possible to identify how DL methods were progressively substituting classic ML approaches in 2018 and 2019. According to the authors of [13], the main advantage of DL against traditional ML was their ability to handle complex transportation scenarios which require predictions at the network level. As stated before, traditional ML methods face limitations when capturing the spatial and temporal relationships of traffic patterns, while DL can handle these temporal and spatial characteristics of traffic data.

Two years later, in 2021, [31] introduced a standard benchmark of DL methods to comprehensively evaluate their performances with the same settings and metrics on widely used datasets. Following this same research line, [34] questioned the benefits and downsides of DL when dealing with TF. First, this study reviewed publications from recent years. Then, a posterior critical analysis was held with a benchmark of diverse TF scenarios. Such experimentation unveiled that DL could not be the best modeling technique for every case, which revealed caveats (like computational complexity of DL models and their black-box nature, high data requirements, data quality and availability etc.) unconsidered to date that the community in prospective studies should address.

Afterwards, [32] surveyed DL models from the perspective of spatial and temporal structure design. The authors stated that existing models could be divided into combinatorial and integrative structures, where the spatial and temporal submodules are considered stepwise with the combinatorial mode but considered comprehensively as a whole with the integrative mode. Furthermore, this paper summarizes the open data sets and source code of the surveyed papers to help upcoming researchers.

In 2022, [30] reviewed the rapidly growing body of research using different graph neural networks (e.g., graph convolutional and graph attention networks), in various TF

problems. The authors also presented a comprehensive list of open data and source codes for each problem and identified future research directions (like, the need for a centralized data repository, unified traffic graph design, fusion with other DNN paradigms, use along with Automated ML (AutoML) and Bayesian Networks, including external factors like weather conditions, etc.).

Afterwards, [35] categorizes Graph Neural Network (GNN) studies based on the different applications of forecasting, autonomous vehicles, demand modeling, etc. They identified that efficient, interpretable, and generalizable GNNs are the main remaining challenges that need to be addressed to enable their applications in the real world. Additionally, transfer learning, graph reinforcement learning, graph learning, and link prediction/estimation are suggested as possible research directions.

Recently, [36] provided a review of literature based on different network representation approaches, which were analyzed and used in proposing future research directions in traffic forecasting. Stacked vector, image/grid and graph representations were considered, and compared in relation to efficiency, accuracy, and modeling techniques. Furthermore, the authors outline various challenges that still need to be addressed in future research, with a key focus on a traffic forecasting framework that can provide network-wide predictions in real-time. Related open issues are explainability, inclusivity, efficiency, and scalability to consider all modes.

In a nutshell, the literature at the point where TF and DL converge is abundant. Various survey and review papers summarize the existing literature and present a landscape where challenges and research directions are discussed. Those contributions are normally derived from theoretical studies and other times, they are extracted from benchmark papers that test the performance and suitability of DL methods in TF scenarios. Despite this, it has been hard to find clear knowledge about best practices for designing DL techniques in TF problems where this data-driven approach can highly contribute. To the best of our knowledge, this paper is the first rigorous attempt to introduce best practices that support researchers and practitioners in applying DL for TF.

In the field of TF, several DL models have been developed, and many can provide real-time inference using modern computers. Recent developments in graph neural networks have led to the many state-of-the-art (SotA) models in the last few years. The goal of this section is to provide a comparison of various DL models to give you a comprehensive picture of the current SotA in the field of TF. The selection of models discussed in this paper is based on the reported results and the popularity and authenticity of the papers. It includes papers that are currently providing SotA results or had a major contribution into the current SotA.

B. STATE-OF-THE-ART MODELS

This section reviews deep learning models developed for traffic forecasting, focusing on spatio-temporal dependencies and handling of complex traffic dynamics. The state-of-the-art models include:

- Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional Network (STGCN) [37] - Utilizes graph-based spatial dependencies and temporal convolutional layers to efficiently predict traffic flows, addressing computational challenges of recurrent models.
- Diffusion Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (DCRNN) [38] - Models traffic as a diffusion process on graphs, capturing both spatial and temporal dependencies. Employs sequence-to-sequence learning with scheduled sampling for robust multistep predictions.
- Graph WaveNet (GWN) [39] – A framework of spatio-temporal layers, which are constructed by a graph convolution layer and a gated temporal convolution layer, with dilated causal convolutions for capturing long-range temporal dependencies.
- Improved GWN [40] - Enhances GWN’s performance through optimized hyperparameters, skip connections, and pretraining on short-term predictions.
- Graph Multi-Attention Network (GMAN) [41] - Combines spatial and temporal attention to adaptively model dynamic correlations and reduce error propagation in long-term predictions.
- Adaptive Graph Convolutional Recurrent Network (AGCRN) [42] - Learns spatial dependencies through adaptive graph generation and node-specific parameter learning, improving spatial accuracy.
- Spatial-Temporal Attention WaveNet (STAWnet) [43] - Employs self-learned embeddings and a dynamic attention network without needing predefined graphs.
- Multivariate Time Series GNN (MTGNN) [44] - Learns spatial dependencies directly from data, through a graph learning layer, graph and temporal convolution modules, suitable for multivariate time series without explicit graph structures.
- Multi-Stream Feature Fusion Method (MFFB) [45] - Multi-stream feature fusion block module which includes GCN, GRU, and a fully connected neural network with soft attention for enhanced feature fusion in traffic prediction.
- Dynamic Graph Convolution Network (DGCN) [46] - Dynamically updates graph structure using Laplace matrices, allowing real-time adaptation to traffic changes.
- CNN-LSTM [12] - Combines convolutional layers and LSTMs for spatio-temporal analysis, effective for both short- and long-term predictions on trajectory data.

More detailed discussions on these models are included below.

1) SPATIO-TEMPORAL GRAPH CONVOLUTIONAL NETWORK (STGCN)

In [37], the authors propose a Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional Network (STGCN) framework for time series prediction problems in traffic domains, where they include complex spatial dependencies by a graph and handle weaknesses of recurrent networks (such as computational expense) by using a fully convolutional structure. In STGCN, two gated sequential convolution layers are sandwiched by a spatial graph convolution layer composed of several spatio-temporal convolutional (ST-Conv) blocks. These blocks are composed of two spatio-temporal convolutional layers and a fully connected output layer. During ST-Conv, the residual connection and bottleneck strategies are applied within each block, which contains two temporal gates and one spatial graph.

2) DIFFUSION CONVOLUTIONAL RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORK (DCRNN)

Another SotA model is described in [38]. It mentions three challenges for TF: complex spatial dependency on road networks, non-linear temporal dynamics with changing road conditions, and the inherent difficulty of long-term forecasting. DCRNN [38] uses a thresholded Gaussian kernel to build the adjacency matrix between the sensors in the sensor graph as a function of the pairwise road network distance between the sensors. It captures both spatial and temporal dependency using bidirectional random walks on the graph, as well as encoder-decoder architectures with scheduled sampling. The Diffusion Convolutional Network filter is a spectral convolutional operator derived by modeling traffic flow as a diffusion process defined by a Markov process. The assumption is that the diffusion process will converge to a stationary distribution after several time steps, and it describes the transition probabilities between nodes. Then, a GRU is built by replacing matrix multiplication with the diffusion convolutional layer. The sequence-to-sequence architecture was employed to enable multistep forecasting. The encoder maps the input to a hidden space, and then the decoder employs this hidden space to forecast future values. The ablation study of DCRNN shows variants of the model by disabling some parts of it to see how they affect the model. Three variants were used in the ablation study:

- DCNN applies stacked diffusion convolutional layers to historical observations and concatenates them into a fixed-length vector. The model uses the previous prediction as input to perform multiple steps ahead predictions.
- DCRNN-SEQ uses the encoder-decoder sequence to sequence learning framework to perform multiple steps ahead forecasting.
- DCRNN differs from DCRNN-SEQ by adding scheduled sampling. That approach for training recurrent neural networks involves feeding the model a mixture of the teacher-forced embeddings and the model predictions from the previous step.

3) GRAPH WAVENET (GWN)

The authors of [39] propose Graph WaveNet (GWN), which uses an adaptive approach to learn the dependency matrix

and node embeddings automatically. An end-to-end supervised training method is proposed for a graph convolution layer that can automatically learn a self-adaptive adjacency matrix from data. The proposed model can work with multivariate time series in which the underlying graph is not defined. They employ stacked dilated one-dimensional causal convolutions in which their receptive fields increase along with the number of layers to capture temporal dependencies. The main advantage of dilated causal convolution networks compared with RNN-based approaches is that they can handle long-range sequences without recursion, which facilitates parallel computation and prevents gradient explosion. Another advantage of this model is that it can output the predictions as a whole instead of providing predictions as input to the model to predict further time series, which minimizes training and inference time extremely.

4) GWN-IMPROVED

The SotA model in [40] improves GWN in performance, primarily because of the usage of better hyperparameters, the addition of skip connections that allow more significant gradients to flow back into the early convolutional layers, and pretraining with an easier short-term traffic prediction problem.

5) GRAPH MULTI-ATTENTION NETWORK (GMAN)

GMAN [41] adopts encoder-decoder architectures to model the impact of spatio-temporal factors on traffic conditions. Three challenges were mentioned by [41] in long-term TF. First, correlations of traffic conditions change significantly over time. To predict traffic conditions for a target sensor in the long term, dynamically selecting sensors' data is challenging. Second, there can be considerable fluctuations in traffic conditions at a sensor caused by an accident, affecting correlations between different time steps. Third, the challenge to model nonlinear temporal correlations further into the future adaptively, because of sensitivity to error propagation in long-term TF. [41] proposes GMAN to address these challenges. It proposes an ST-Attention block for the encoder and the decoder. These blocks are made of spatial attention mechanisms to model dynamic spatial correlations, temporal attention mechanisms for nonlinear temporal correlations modeling, and gated fusion mechanisms for spatio-temporal representations. They also propose a direct relationship between historical and future time steps to alleviate the problem of error propagation.

6) ADAPTIVE GRAPH CONVOLUTIONAL RECURRENT NETWORK (AGCRN)

In [42], the authors discuss that the predefined graph cannot represent thorough information about spatial dependency, and a method for learning the graph structure is required. They also mention that weight sharing among nodes significantly diminishes the capability of learning the correlations between sensors. They propose two modules to handle the mentioned problem. A Node Adaptive Parameter Learning (NAPL) module, which learns node-specific correlations and a Data Adaptive Graph Generation (DAGG) module, which calculates the underlying graph automatically

based on the sensor values. Chebyshev polynomials can approximate graph convolution operations and can be generalized to multi-dimensional GCNs [47]. They replace the proposed GCN with matrix multiplication in GRU for the temporal part.

7) SPATIAL-TEMPORAL ATTENTION WAVENET (STAWNET)

Spatial-Temporal Attention Wavenet (STAWnet) is proposed in [43]. It mentions two challenges in traffic forecasting using stationary graphs. First, spatial information is sometimes unavailable due to secrecy or privacy; and even when it is available, it might be inaccurate. The second challenge is that spatial dependencies have dynamic characteristics that evolve over time. As in the recent trend in TF, STAWnet does not need prior knowledge of the graph, and it learns that by developing a self-learned node embedding. Multiple ST-blocks make up the STAWnet. Each ST-block in the STAWnet comprises a gated TCN and a DAN (dynamic attention network), where node embedding is integrated. Layer normalization is utilized in each ST-block to prevent overfitting. To speed up convergence, residual and skip connections are employed throughout the network. To compute the predictions, the skip outputs from gated TCNs are added together, then passed through output layers.

8) MULTIVARIATE TIME SERIES FORECASTING WITH GRAPH NEURAL NETWORKS (MTGNN)

In [44], the authors propose a general GNN for multivariate time series data to address unknown graph structures and graph learning. For the first challenge, they claim that in most cases, multivariate time series does not have an explicit graph structure, and most GNN approaches rely heavily on pre-defined graph structures. Data must reveal the variables' relationships rather than a user providing it as ground truth knowledge. For the second challenge, they claim that most GNN approaches overlook the fact that even when an underlying graph is known, the graph structure is not optimal and should be updated during training. [44] proposes a graph learning module to learn hidden spatial dependencies among variables and a framework named MTGNN that can handle multivariate time series regardless of whether they are structured as graphs. MTGNN is composed of three modules: a graph learning layer, graph convolution modules, temporal convolution modules, and an output module. An adjacency matrix is computed by the graph learning layer and fed to the graph convolution modules. Graph convolution modules are mixed with temporal convolution modules to capture spatiotemporal dependencies. The gradient vanishing problem is avoided by adding residual connections from temporal convolution to graph convolution.

9) MULTI-STREAM FEATURE FUSION (MFFB) METHOD

[45] proposes a method for traffic flow prediction using a multi-stream feature fusion method. An important part of this approach is the use of data-driven adjacency matrix which is initialized using the Spearman rank correlation coefficient between monitoring stations to represent the road network.

This adjacency matrix is then updated during the model training procedure to decrease the loss value. The model incorporates a multi-stream feature fusion block that integrates a GCN, a GRU, and a Fully Connected Neural Network to extract spatial, temporal, and auxiliary features, respectively. This fusion is accompanied by a soft-attention mechanism that prioritizes more significant features dynamically. The paper includes an ablation study to examine the models without GCN, GRU, Fully Connected Neural Network, and without the attention mechanism. The results show that each component positively impacts the prediction performance and they found that GCN has the most impact. Additionally, the proposed model demonstrates efficient training and inference times.

10) DYNAMIC GRAPH CONVOLUTION NETWORK (DGCN)

The authors in [46] propose a dynamic graph convolution network (DGCN) that adaptively constructs dynamic Laplace matrices of road networks to address the limitations of static graph representation. The difference between their proposed method and traditional GCNs is dynamically updating graph structure using a Laplace Matrix Latent Network that captures the spatial-temporal relationships based on the current traffic data. The proposed method then integrates the spatial and temporal dependencies directly within the network structure through graph convolutions that adjust dynamically to the changing graph characteristics.

11) CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK – LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY (CNN-LSTM)

As a final paper, we refer to [12], which focuses on trajectory data and proposes a graph CNN-LSTM architecture. Approaches that combine graph CNNs, and RNNs have shown a superior performance than RNNs and graph CNNs separately. The authors propose a deep neural network that considers traffic's geographical and temporal aspects to create short- and long-term predictions. The latter was still an open issue in literature since the focus was on short-term predictions. Furthermore, they suggest using temporal correlation to reduce the data set and select the most crucial road links. Furthermore, they propose a data reduction approach to identify the most relevant road links for forecasting. An architecture for trajectory data is presented, with two variations that differ primarily in the CNN's layer. The first uses the standard convolution and max-pooling layers, while the other uses max pooling before convolution to reduce the input data's dimension even more without losing important information.

C. COMPARISON STATE-OF-THE-ART MODELS BASED ON GUIDELINES

This section compares the SotA models discussed in section A based on the guidelines for developing robust prediction models that were discussed in section II. It connects the bounty of options that were dealt with by the researchers (based on the guidelines) who presented these SotA models.

This comparison is made in this section, of which an overview is given in Table I.

- **Scope and usage**

The scope of all the SotA models that were discussed in the previous section is all related to traffic supply forecasting. The supply is mostly measured by the traffic speed, volume, and flow as shown in Table I.

The application: The training time for different models vary, but once trained, all SotA models can make real-time predictions on a GPU.

 - **Local and network level predictions**

SotA models can predict several hundred predetermined locations, such as loop detectors in the road network. However, they cannot make predictions for the entire road network, particularly in areas without available measurements.
 - **Prediction horizon**

The prediction horizon is outlined in Table I.
- **Data needs:** traffic data can be provided by loop detectors or by GPS data. Table I lists the data where the SotA models are applied on with their corresponding granularity and quantity. Common datasets used to benchmark in literature are: BJER, PeMSD7, PeMS-BAY, PeMSD4, PeMSD8, METR-LA, Xiamen, and DiDi. These datasets are commonly used and referenced in literature for benchmarking state-of-the-art models in traffic forecasting tasks, since each offer unique patterns that can happen in different urban settings in different cities, countries, and continents.
- **Modeling strategy:** these papers focus is on DL models since they can extract the spatial and temporal relations of the road network and imitate its complex and non-linear mechanisms.
- **Model output evaluation**
 - **Error metric:** the MAE is most popular in literature. Note that the error metrics are not directly comparable between models of very different complexities and datasets with different sizes and characteristics, but therefore the used datasets are mentioned in Table I, together with the achieved MAE. However, since most of them are datasets that are common use in literature, a comparison can often be made.
 - **Complexity:** Factors influencing complexity include the architecture of the model (e.g., number of layers, type of layers such as convolutional or recurrent, use of attention mechanisms), the number of parameters to be estimated (model size), and the intricacies of the optimization algorithm. Models with a high complexity may achieve lower MAEs due to their ability to capture and learn more complicated patterns and relationships

within the data. However, this comes with a risk of overfitting and increased computational costs. Therefore, complexity should be carefully balanced against the needs and limitations of the problem.

- **Time-consuming training process:** besides the achieved MAE, the learning rate and batch size are added in Table I. These are two important hyperparameters used for training the DL models. When they were mentioned in the corresponding papers, we've added them to compare the training process of the different SotA models.
 - **Interpretable results:** surveyed papers in traffic forecasting lack interpretable methods, which can be valuable for future directions in the field. By incorporating more interpretable models into research, we can better understand the underlying processes and factors driving traffic patterns. This knowledge can inform more robust models, and interpretable forecasting models can contribute more to traffic management. Interpretative models might also shape future city planning strategies.
- **Implementation:** all the methods discussed are DL models, which make the inference in real-time possible by using a single modern GPU.

Some technical details regarding the training process were added to Table I. A less technical summary is included here. Considering its accuracy and speed, STGCN can be used as a benchmark for developing novel spatio-temporal DL models. DCRNN suffers less from error propagation due to its ability to deal with mistakes multiple steps ahead of prediction, and they claim that the bidirectional random walk captures downstream and upstream traffic's influence. GWN's inference performance on the validation data shows that it is five times faster than DCRNN but twice as slow as STGCN in training. Evaluation of the inference efficiency of GWN is based on its total time cost over the validation data. The performance gain is caused by the fact that GWN generates 12 predictions in one run. On the contrary, DCRNN and STGCN produce results based on past predictions. Using several hyperparameter adjustments, a decrease in MAE of 0.03 is achieved by GWN-improved compared to the original GWN. Another conclusion of [40] is that pretraining on a subset of a 1-hour prediction horizon window and then training on a full dataset improves MAE by 0.01 as well. GMAN reports comparable inference time with GWN and, like GWN, produces 12 step ahead predictions in one run. STAWNETH reports state-of-the-art results with fewer inputs compared with related studies (DCRNN, STGCN, Graph WaveNet). The architecture of CNN-LSTM can work with GPS traffic data. It introduces a

data reduction technique based on time-related correlation to select relevant road links from a city-wide network. The model can work for short-term (5 min) and long-term (up to 4 h) predictions.

Furthermore, the overview of performance based on accuracy is visualized in Fig. 1. The used error metric is the Mean Absolute Error, which is shown for the datasets METR-LA and PeMS-BAY at a prediction horizon of 60min. The other datasets, mentioned in Table I, are only used by one of the surveyed papers, and therefore not comparable over all the different SotA models. It can be concluded that all included models have a good accuracy on these datasets commonly used in literature (METR-LA and PeMS-BAY). In the TANGENT project existing and improved methods will be further investigated in the context of supply forecasting in the four pilot cities Athens, Lisbon, Greater Manchester, and Rennes Métropole.

Table II lists the primary challenges addressed by each paper. There are challenges regarding working with trajectory data, working with incomplete or unavailable road networks (unknown graph structure), modeling with an evolving graph structure, handling spatial correlations among sensors, handling non-linear temporal correlations, and making predictions in a single run rather than recursively putting the model's predictions into its own models. GWN-Improved addresses the same challenges as GWN and is therefore not addressed in the table, and STGCN doesn't mention specific challenges.

Dealing with trajectory data poses significant challenges due to its typical large-scale nature, inherent noise, and additional requirements such as map-matching for it to be useful. For the second point, the flexibility to operate with unfamiliar graph structures enables the model to manage instances where data are either unattainable or difficult to procure due more effectively to privacy or other concerns. Additionally, working with the evolving structure of a graph, illustrated by the construction of new roads and bridges in a road network or blockage of a highway, necessitates the ability to capture and learn the shifting relationships and connections between nodes as the graph develops. This dynamic quality adds a layer of complexity to the process. Regarding spatial correlations among sensors, this refers to the mutual dependence or relationship between diverse sensors or data points in space. This is a challenging aspect because it calls for recognizing and incorporating spatial dependencies into the predictive modeling process. Spatial correlations among sensors refer to the relationship or dependence between different sensors in a road network. Addressing this aspect is quite challenging as it requires recognizing and incorporating spatial dependencies into the predictive modeling process. Temporal correlations, on the other hand, relate to the interdependencies between data points across time. Non-linear temporal correlations present an obstacle because they necessitate the recognition and capture of complex and non-linear patterns or trends in the

data. Conventional linear models may not accurately capture these patterns. As for the latest challenge mentioned above, making predictions in a single run, rather than recursively feeding the model's predictions back into itself like in autoregressive models, has its own challenges. The main challenge is the computational costs associated with such models. However, these models typically provide more accurate predictions and faster inference times.

IV. DISCUSSION

Recently, the authors of [30] listed some research gaps: Many publications consider a limited period, most commonly less than a year, in their testing and training procedures. This cannot represent all the traffic patterns. Additionally, many publications analyze cleaned datasets that do not reflect real world scenarios. Furthermore, these do not contain enough anomaly data for DL training procedures, resulting in many methods' inability to consider these events in their forecasting. Also, a limited number of publications work on transfer learning which could be beneficial in forecasting traffic in cities without enough traffic data.

Furthermore, two major research tracks related to traffic forecasting with deep learning are:

- developing efficient representations of multi-modal traffic networks [37] and
- efficient large-scale forecasts based on historical data on short to medium time (up to 4 hours) horizons, flexible and applied on different transport modes [48].

To end the discussion about challenges, Table III summarizes the challenges and possible contributions that the authors of this paper are facing in the TANGENT project.

V. CONCLUSION

As a Research and Innovation Action, TANGENT will address several advances beyond the state-of-the-art. One addressed topic is the field of traffic predictions and simulations. This paper gives an overview of best practices that are used in the current state-of-the-art models for traffic supply forecasting, by focusing on guidelines for developing robust prediction models. The guidelines are proposed for researchers and practitioners in order to develop accurate and robust prediction models: define scope, usage, requirements for the forecasting applications; determine whether they are performed on a local or network-wide level; define the desirable prediction horizon (short-term versus long-term prediction); define the data needs that are necessary to perform the predictions; define the modeling strategy from the different available methods; determine the tools needed for the model development; decide on the evaluation strategy for its results; fine-tune the model; consider generalization concerning the use of an already developed model; move to real-world exploitation by ensuring the previous steps. The discussed state-of-the-art models are deep learning models, since with the ever-growing data-collection, deep learning

techniques started to improve and surpassed the traditional methods in performance. Several state-of-the-art models were presented in this paper with a focus on their highlights, their possible prediction horizons, learning rate, batch size, performance, model evaluation, possibilities regarding generalization, ... Furthermore, the paper identifies possible challenges in traffic forecasting, which helps in assisting practitioners in the model selection.

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Figure 1. Visualization of performance (accuracy). This comparison is based on the Mean Absolute Error with a prediction horizon of 60 min for datasets commonly used in literature, namely METR-LA and PeMS-BAY.

TABLE I: STATE-OF-THE-ART MODELS: SUMMARY BASED ON GUIDELINES

Model	STGCN [37]	DCRNN [38]	GWN [39]	GWN-improved [40]	GMAN [41]	AGCRN [42]	STAWNET [43]	MTGNN [44]	MFFB [45]	DGCN [46]	CNN-LSTM [12]
Scope: supply measured by	Flow, Speed	Speed	Speed	Speed	Vol, Speed	Flow	Speed, Flow	Speed	Flow, Speed	Flow	Speed
Highlights	One of the first to apply Graph Convolution in TF	Propose diffusion convolution, Thresholded Gaussian Kernel to calculate adjacency matrix	Learns adjacency matrix, TCN for temporal dependency. Whole prediction is done in a single run.	Adding several improve ments to Graph WaveNet	Spatio-temporal Transformer (Attention mechanism), Whole prediction is done in a single run	Learns adjacency matrix	Learns evolution of adjacency matrix over time	Learns evolution of adjacency matrix over time	Adjacency matrix updated during model training	Dynamically updating graph structure using a Laplace Matrix Latent Network	Data reduction, Trajectory data
Application: prediction horizon (min)	15/30/45	15/30/60	15/30/60	15/30/60	15/30/60	60	5/15/30/60	15/30/60	15/30/60	60	5/240
Traffic data: granularity	Two 5-minute granularity loop detector datasets	Two 5-minute granularity loop detector datasets	Same as DCRNN	Same as DCRNN	Two 5-minute granularity loop detector datasets	Two 5-minute granularity loop detector datasets	Three 5-minute granularity loop detector datasets	Same as DCRNN	Two 5-minute granularity loop detector datasets	Two 5-minute granularity loop detector datasets	5-minute trajectory data
Traffic data: period	Two datasets: one spanning 37 weekdays and the other covering two months excluding weekends	Two datasets: one spanning four months and the other covering six months	Same as DCRNN	Same as DCRNN	Two datasets: spanning five months and the other covering six months	Two datasets: spanning two months	Three datasets: one spanning six months and the others covering four months	Same as DCRNN	Two datasets spanning six months	Two datasets spanning two months	One dataset spanning two months
Model output evaluation - Training process: learning rate	10^{-3} with a decay rate of 0.7 after every 5 epochs	10^{-2} divided by 10 every 10 epochs after 20th epoch	10^{-2}	10^{-2} with a decay rate 0.97 every epoch	10^{-3}	-	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	-	0.0005 with decay rates 0.92 every epoch	-
Model output evaluation - Training process: batch	50	-	-	64	-	-	64	64	-	-	-
Model output evaluation - Loss (MAE per prediction horizon as given in column 4)	BJER: 3.78/4.45/5.03 PeMSD7(M): 2.25/3.03/3.57 PeMSD7(L): 2.37/3.27/3.97	METR-LA: 2.77/3.15/3.60 PeMS-BAY: 1.38/1.74/2.07	METR-LA: 2.69/3.07/3.53 PeMS-BAY: 1.30/1.63/1.95	METR-LA: 2.64/3.03/3.47 PeMS-BAY: 1.34/1.62/1.86	Xiamen: 11.50/12.02/12.79 PeMS-BAY: 1.34/1.62/1.86	PeMSD4: 19.83 PeMSD8: 15.95	METR-LA: 2.28/2.70/3.04/3.44 PeMS-BAY: 0.86/1.31/1.62/1.89 PeMSO7: 1.32/1.65/1.94 PeMSO7: 16.97/18.74/20.09/22.21	METR-LA: 2.69/3.05/3.49 PeMS-BAY: 1.36/1.68/1.98	PeMSD4: 22.19/23.91/26.19 PeMS-BAY: 1.36/1.68/1.98	PeMSD4: 19.60 PeMSD8: 15.19	DIDI: 3.43/4.034

TABLE II
CHALLENGES IN TRAFFIC SUPPLY FORECASTING HANDLED BY EACH MODEL

Challenge	DCRNN	GWN	GMAN	AGCRN	STAWNET	MTGNN	CNN-LSTM
Trajectory data	O	O	O	O	O	O	P
Unknown graph structure	O	P	O	P	P	P	O
Evolving graph structure	O	O	O	O	P	P	O
Complex spatial correlations among sensors	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Non-linear temporal correlations	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Predictions in a single run	O	P	P	O	O	O	O

TABLE III
CHALLENGES AND POSSIBLE CONTRIBUTIONS

Challenges	Possible contributions
Use information from demand side in traffic supply prediction	Connection between supply and demand
Data resolution, aggregation, and quality (limited period, no cleaned datasets)	Determine degree of aggregation, check data availability and quality in real world scenarios, robust data processing containing imputation and denoising is needed for the robust DL TF solution
Network-wide data availability: DL models need a consistent data stream for training and inference Without simulation not possible to give predictions on new traffic modes	Hybrid approaches that combine the strengths of forecasting and simulation to get network-wide traffic state predictions Hybrid approaches that combine the strengths of forecasting and simulation such as using simulated data to train forecasting algorithm on new traffic modes for which there is no historic data available yet (such as CAVs)
Transfer learning	Examine the effectiveness of transfer learning when not enough traffic data is available for a certain city
Robustness to Outliers and Anomalies: Traffic patterns can be disrupted by factors such as accidents, road closures, and events.	DL models inherently learn these patterns and predict future values if similar ones happen in the training data. However, the solution can help traffic managers by adding anomaly detection algorithms that can cause alarms for emergency services